

Electronic Lab Notebooks in Microbiology – Advancing FAIR and Open Research

Justine Vandendorpe (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9421-8582>)¹,
Catherine Gonzalez (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7585-9990>)²,
Anke Becker (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4561-9184>)³, Carsten
Fortmann-Grote (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2579-5546>)⁴,
Carolin Kaufhold-Wedel
(<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6730-2220>)^{5, 6}, Daniel Kelvin
(<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4563-6216>)⁷, Negin Pirhadi
(<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7991-2887>)^{8, 9}, Manuela Reuter
(<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-5191-3414>)⁴, T. Nicolai Siegel
(<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1715-7907>)^{8, 9}, Beatrix Suess
(<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8666-6716>)⁷, Michael-Paul
Vockenhuber (<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8111-1723>)³, and
Konrad U. Förstner
(<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8251-1597>)^{1, 10, *}

¹Data Science & Services, ZB MED - Information Centre for Life Sciences, Cologne, NRW, Germany

²IT Center, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, NRW, Germany

³Center for Synthetic Microbiology (SYNMIKRO),
Philipps-Universität Marburg, Marburg, HE, Germany

⁴Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology, Dept. of
Microbial Population Biology, Plön, SH, Germany

⁵Ludwig Maximilian University, Planegg-Martinsried, BY,
Germany

⁶Tissue Bank of the National Center for Tumor Diseases (NCT)
Heidelberg, Heidelberg University Hospital, Heidelberg, BW,
Germany

⁷Synthetic RNA biology, TU Darmstadt, Darmstadt, HE,
Germany

⁸Division of Experimental Parasitology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Munich, BY, Germany

⁹Biomedical Center, Division of Physiological Chemistry, Faculty of Medicine, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Munich, BY, Germany

¹⁰Faculty of Information Science and Communication Studies, TH Köln – University of Applied Sciences, Cologne, NRW, Germany

*Corresponding author: Konrad U. Förstner, Data Science and Services, ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences, Gleueler Str. 60, 50931 Cologne, NRW, Germany, foerstner@zbmed.de

2025-07-03

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15797347>

Abstract

Electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) are software tools designed to document experiments, research data and processes. As part of the ongoing digital transformation in scientific research, these digital tools will eventually replace traditional paper lab notebooks. In the field of microbiology, ELNs offer numerous advantages, including enhanced efficiency in daily tasks, seamless integration with digital research environments, improved reproducibility, adherence to FAIR data principles, and promotion of good research practice. In this article, we discuss these benefits and compare proprietary and open-source ELNs. In addition, we explore the culture change required for the transition from physical to electronic lab notebooks and present testimonials from microbiologists who have successfully navigated this transition.

1 PERSPECTIVE

In many scientific disciplines, including microbiology, documenting experimental setups and results in lab notebooks is an essential part of the research process. This centuries-old practice has traditionally relied on physical lab notebooks. However, the advent of digitalisation has transformed this aspect of scientific documentation.

Figure 1: Enhancing Microbiology Research with Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs).

Electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) transform the way scientists document their research, offering a host of advantages over conventional methods (Fig 1). Yet, despite the potential benefits of ELNs, many laboratories have been reluctant to put them into widespread use. Various hurdles need to be overcome before these digital tools can be fully integrated into research workflows and data management strategies.

The concept of ELNs gained significant attention in August 1993 when an entire day of the 206th National Meeting of the American Chemical Society was devoted to discussing their potential [5]. These discussions highlighted several key objectives for ELNs. The primary goal was to replace physical notebooks in laboratories: ELNs would enable the capture of vast amounts of experimental data that could be stored securely and searched far more easily than paper records. In addition, they would provide automated audits of laboratory records, a crucial part of the authentication process required to file patents or

Table 1: Benefits of ELNs over physical lab notebooks in various use cases

Aspect of use	Uses of physical lab notebooks	Additional uses of ELNs	Benefits
Documentation	Documentation of experiments, resulting research data and processes	Annotation of raw data with tags or metadata Closer ties between data and their description through embedded multimedia files and links to shared resources, other experiments, datasets and workflows	Data are searchable, discoverable, traceable and reusable No need to switch between media formats
Collaboration	Communication of your work	Sharing of information about the project, data and documentation	Reduced need for meetings
Good research practice (GRP)	Legal document: evidence in patent disputes and defence against allegations of scientific misconduct	Electronic signatures, access management, timestamping to prevent further changes, audit trail, version control of experiment description Preventing data loss: ELNs are fire- and waterproof, they cannot be lost, misplaced or stolen, and they can be automatically backed up	Tracking, tracing and documentation of research process; providing data security
Reputation	Scientific legacy in the lab		Full data provenance available
Lab management		Managing inventories of samples, reagents and other supplies Tracking equipment and equipment maintenance schedule	More efficient lab work

obtain Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval [23]. In 1997, Kodak developed the first ELN, implemented as a collection of Lotus Notes databases and applications. In 1998, one of the first web-based ELNs, Virtual Notebook Environment, was released [5]. Early ELNs were often discipline-specific, had limited functionality, and lacked the ability to connect to other systems. They also faced technical limitations such as low storage capacity, cumbersome ergonomics, and low levels of security. The 2000s marked a significant evolution in ELN technology, driven by the rise of the Internet and cloud computing. This led to ELNs becoming more powerful, versatile and accessible [19]. By 2022, the ELN market had grown significantly, with 96 active ELNs reported [8, 5]. Yet despite the increased use of ELNs in both research and commercial laboratories [4], there is still some resistance to their adoption within the scientific community [5].

Although ELNs can be thought of as the electronic equivalent of physical lab notebooks, their capabilities go far beyond simply digitising the research process (Table 1). ELNs offer numerous advantages over their physical counterparts, enhancing collaboration and significantly improving efficiency in various aspects of scientific work.

In this article, we discuss the benefits of ELNs for microbiologists, explore strategies for making a successful transition from physical to electronic lab notebooks, and examine the differences between proprietary and open-source ELNs.

1.1 Benefits of ELNs for microbiologists

1.1.1 Increased efficiency in daily tasks

ELNs enhance the efficiency of everyday tasks by providing ubiquitous access: protocols, observations, notes and other data can be entered and edited using a multitude of devices [17], including computers and tablets. ELNs also provide time-saving features including copy-and-paste functionality, linking of experiments and samples via QR codes, and extensive search capabilities that extend beyond individual files, such as finding a gel image within an entire project. In addition, they leverage standardisation [16] by enabling the creation of templates such as protocols [22], standard operating procedures (SOPs) and workflows. This facilitates the documentation of data with metadata [22, 27] and supports the clarity and organisation of protocols and data [28]. Finally, ELNs can handle volume and complexity requirements more effectively than their physical counterparts [8]. In the future, with ELNs as the underlying platform, the integration of AI-driven features can further improve the efficiency of the research process. These features could include bi-directional voice interfaces for interacting with your ELN, automated suggestions for metadata and tags, and recommendations for further experiments.

1.1.2 Seamless data integration

ELNs offer superior data integration compared to physical lab notebooks. For example, they eliminate the need to stick or tape gel images to a page in a notebook. Instead, images and graphs can be uploaded directly into the experiment documentation on the ELN.

ELNs can also be linked to a digital research environment [11] through their import and export capabilities [2], especially if they support an open-exchange format [27] such as the ELN File Format [3]. The ELN File Format was developed to enhance interoperability between different ELN software solutions [3]. In general, interoperability can be achieved through the use of open standards, which then enable datasets to be read and written by different systems. The ELN File Format enables researchers to export experiment documentation and share it with collaborators at other institutions who may be using different ELN software. This format allows collaborators to view the documentation and continue documenting their experiments in their own ELN.

ELNs can also be integrated with upstream and downstream systems such as laboratory equipment, programming languages, software and data management platforms [27], for example through application programming interfaces (APIs) [2]. These networking capabilities enable ELNs to play a central role in an institution's research data management (RDM) strategy [27].

1.1.3 Better reproducibility

ELNs also contribute significantly to reproducibility in scientific research. Reproducibility, as defined by Schloss 2018 [20], is the ability to regenerate a result using the same dataset and data analysis workflow. Specific threats to reproducibility identified by Schloss in microbiology include the lack of publicly accessible raw sequencing data and associated metadata that contextualise the sequencing data, inadequate documentation of the evolution of resources and what are considered best practices, and what Schloss calls "link rot", where methods and protocols become inaccessible due to outdated web or email addresses [20].

These threats to reproducibility can be mitigated by using an ELN. First, ELNs support the FAIR data principles [27], which ensure that researchers make their data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (see next section for more details). For example, when researchers publish their results, they must publish the accompanying data, annotated with the necessary metadata, which can be facilitated by ELNs. Second, ELNs streamline the documentation of data collection and workflows, for example by providing templates for protocols [22] and workflows. Human-readable protocols can also be included in Research Object Crate (RO-Crate) bundles [24], which package resources with their associated metadata to support FAIR publication and archiving of research data [22]. ELNs also provide versioning (e.g. of experiment descriptions) [18], and some ELNs can integrate literate programming tools such as Jupyter Notebook (e.g. openBIS [15]). Finally, ELNs facilitate data sharing and can help prepare data for publication and digital preservation [27]. Overall, ELNs make the research process more transparent and traceable, thereby improving reproducibility.

1.1.4 Compliance with FAIR data principles

ELNs help researchers comply with the FAIR data principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) [17], a concise set of measurable guidelines designed to enhance the reusability of scientific data [31]. Wilkinson *et al.* [31] developed these principles to improve data mapping (i.e. the process of matching fields between datasets [26]), particularly for classical experiments stored in specialised repositories. Their work also aimed to enhance data discovery by enabling targeted and effective searches for reusable data. Finally, they wanted datasets to clearly indicate whether they can be downloaded for reuse and, if so, under what conditions [9]. The FAIR data principles thus benefit researchers by making it easier to reuse datasets (or parts of datasets) and to integrate them into new datasets.

ELNs support findability by helping to assign and manage metadata, tags (e.g. through extraction from documents) and persistent identifiers (PIDs).

PIDs are globally unique, actionable and machine-resolvable strings that act as a permanent reference to a digital object. An example of a PID is the Digital Object Identifier (DOI), which is used to uniquely identify digital objects (e.g. research data, text publications) to make them easily findable online. ELNs also support findability by linking to data repositories and digital preservation systems [2] (see examples in [27]).

ELNs also support interoperability by allowing the use of controlled vocabularies (i.e. an organised arrangement of words and phrases that are used to index and/or retrieve content through browsing and searching [7, 25, 14]) in metadata. Some ELNs also allow export to a standard format [2] such as the ELN File Format [3].

Finally, ELNs support reusability by providing detailed provenance information through audit trails (i.e. chronological logs of all previous versions of a note) and through the documentation of data generation (e.g. method logs) and equipment used [2].

1.1.5 Contribution to good research practice (GRP)

The loss of scientific data documented in physical lab notebooks is a significant issue, exemplified by the case of Charles Kettering and Thomas Midgley Jr., two American engineers who worked for General Motors (GM). Their groundbreaking work on tetraethyl lead (TEL) as a fuel additive, later linked to lead poisoning, is now untraceable due to the disappearance of lab notebooks, meeting minutes, reports on alternatives to TEL, workers' medical records and other relevant documents. It appears that GM's lead archives have been "sanitised" [29, 10].

ELNs can prevent such cases and support good research practice (GRP) by facilitating the tracking, tracing and documentation of research processes and results over time [27]. They offer features such as electronic signatures, version control [12], authentication, 'freezing' of work status, searchability and tagging of entries, and audit trails [2]. ELNs also prevent data loss caused by deletion [2], illegible handwriting, media discontinuities between handwritten and digital entries, damaged paper notebooks and the departure of researchers [17]. Furthermore, ELNs contribute to GRP by ensuring data security and facilitating collaboration.

1.2 Proprietary vs. open-source ELNs

When selecting an ELN, as with any other software used in the research process, a key factor to consider is whether to opt for a proprietary or open-source solution. Higgins *et al.* have outlined several key points to consider when making this choice [8]: Proprietary ELNs have the advantage of being easy to

deploy and are typically developed by vendors who provide software updates (security and new features) as part of the subscription. However, proprietary ELNs can be expensive and their closed-source nature means that third parties must rely on the company to identify and fix security vulnerabilities. The development of new features is often dictated by the company's priorities rather than user needs, and there is a risk of data becoming inaccessible if the vendor increases prices or ceases operations. Proprietary ELNs mostly use proprietary formats, which can lead to vendor lock-in, making it difficult for users to migrate their data to another ELN without significant costs [30]).

Open-source ELNs are in most cases less expensive than their proprietary counterparts, even when total cost of ownership (TCO) is taken into account, and can leverage resources already available within your organisation. A major advantage of open-source ELNs is their contribution to digital sovereignty. This allows for customisation to meet discipline-specific needs, with users able to suggest new features, develop their own applications, share their work in a documented way and observe other users' developments. Open-source ELNs also provide flexibility in data backup, storage and preservation, giving users full control over data location and accessibility, while their public codebase allows for broader scrutiny, enabling quicker identification of security issues. Finally, digital sovereignty means that you retain unlimited access to all notebook entries and files, with built-in export capabilities or the option to create custom data extraction methods.

However, open-source ELNs can be time-consuming to run and maintain, and they may require skills and/or hardware to implement, unless managed by a service provider. For instance, the open-source ELN eLabFTW offers a hosted solution where installation, hosting, maintenance and backups are handled by Deltablot, the company behind eLabFTW [6]). Open-source ELNs do not have a fixed, vendor-defined set of features, and users interact with a community of developers rather than a single vendor for software maintenance, such as patching security vulnerabilities or developing new features. Data security for open-source ELNs requires ongoing monitoring and verification, which could complicate regulatory compliance [8].

In conclusion, we recommend using an open-source ELN. If this is not feasible, opt for a commercial ELN that supports an open-exchange format. If no such format is available, choose an ELN that uses a widely interoperable format such as XML or JSON. For a more detailed comparison of open-source and proprietary ELNs, refer to Table 2 in Higgins et al. 2022 [8].

1.3 Transition and culture change

To transition researchers from physical to electronic lab notebooks, a culture change is required. Nosek 2019 [13] identifies five levels of intervention to ini-

tiate culture and behaviour change: infrastructure, user interface/experience, community, incentives and policy.

Providing the right infrastructure is crucial to helping researchers make the transition. For instance, institutions could cover the cost of using an ELN rather than leaving it to individually funded research projects. It is also necessary to ensure all technical requirements are met, including a stable wireless internet connection and appropriate end devices with up-to-date hardware and software [8]. Suitable devices might include tablets that can be operated while wearing gloves or that come with a stylus for use with gloved hands. Tablets also need to be protected from liquids and, depending on the lab's biosafety level, may require a special casing. By providing access to ELNs via appropriate devices that remain in the lab, an ELN can prevent the easy contamination of both physical and electronic lab notebooks [8].

To ensure that researchers have a positive experience with the ELN, it is important to provide a user-friendly interface, appropriate training, and integration of the ELN into existing workflows. According to Schneikart and Mayrhofer [21], a major disadvantage of ELNs compared to their physical counterparts is their reliance on computers. Many researchers find physical lab notebooks more intuitive, allowing for easy note-taking, sketching, and pasting of images. Again, a user-friendly interface can play a vital role in the transition from physical to electronic lab notebooks: an ELN tablet interface should offer the flexibility to write notes or drag and drop images, providing the familiar feel of a physical lab notebook while digitizing the data and documentation.

Creating communities around ELNs can help normalise their use. Researchers can share their experiences by establishing or joining communities within or outside of their institutions. These communities can focus on user support, resources, solutions and development (in the case of open-source ELNs) [27].

Offering incentives can motivate researchers to adopt ELNs. For example, an ELN can facilitate data publication, and over 100 journals now offer badges indicating whether data or materials are available to the reader.

Lastly, institutions can formalise the use of ELNs in a policy.

We firmly believe that the microbiology community, like other disciplines, will benefit greatly from the use of ELNs, gaining the efficiency, transparency and reproducibility outlined above. We have compiled some user testimonials to help the reader envision this.

1.4 User testimonials

1.4.1 Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology - Focus: links to other systems

Since 2018, the Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology (MPI) has been using openBIS as its ELN and LIMS solution. Initially requested by a single research group, openBIS later became the standard for all researchers at MPI. The primary reason for choosing openBIS was its open-source nature, coupled with professional maintenance and support comparable to commercial ELN services.

This combination of open-source flexibility and professional support, together with the new features requested by users, made it easy to adapt the ELN to the specific needs of research groups. Adaptations have so far included defining new objects and collection types, adding custom controlled vocabularies, and linking to third-party tools and data resources. For example, openBIS is linked to the MPI instance of the OMERO image database [1], its sequence data archive and its strain/sample database. Currently, users can link and reference image and dataset IDs and URLs from OMERO in their ELN. MPI plans to strengthen this integration with OMERO so that OMERO objects (i.e. images, datasets, projects) are represented by corresponding objects in openBIS, including metadata, and to enable annotation of these entities in both services. For the sequence data archive, the path to a sequencing run data directory is a mandatory entry in the Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) dataset object, which is part of the sequence ordering workflow. The Microbial Population Biology Lab (MPB) strain database is synchronised daily with the strain collection in openBIS, and a Python library has been developed to use the openBIS Python API for creating, updating and deleting openBIS records.

Some challenges remain with openBIS: it can appear overly complex and confusing to new users, there are gaps in the documentation, and its JSON API does not conform to the JSON-LD standard.

Overall, however, the use of openBIS has significantly improved work in the MPB lab. OpenBIS has streamlined wet lab work, particularly in executing complex multi-step protocols and collecting counting, imaging and sequencing data. It enhances experiment workflow by breaking down experiments into individual steps, providing a structured daily overview, and clearly linking data to experiments. The uniform structure of protocols and data attachments facilitates experiment replication and improves data accessibility for individual users and other laboratory members.

1.4.2 Technical University of Darmstadt – Focus: transition

Since 2022, the Synthetic RNA Biology lab at the Technical University (TU) of Darmstadt has been using eLabFTW to collect raw data and document wet lab experiments.

The transition from physical lab notebooks to eLabFTW was smooth. TU Darmstadt provided eLabFTW as an application on official servers, making it the easiest and most logical choice of ELN. All lab members, as well as students currently working on theses in the lab, were granted access to eLabFTW, and most were able to use the new tool from day one. While lab computers are available to make entries in eLabFTW, most lab members use their own devices.

eLabFTW makes it possible to keep documentation consistent, especially for projects involving several researchers and students, making it a good collaborative tool. It simplifies tracking and tracing of previous work and documentation while also facilitating the management of multiple concurrent projects.

The use of eLabFTW has been made mandatory for all new members, with a transition period for existing members.

Overall, the switch from physical lab notebooks to eLabFTW has been a great improvement.

1.4.3 Philipps-Universität Marburg - Focus: good research practice

At the Center for Synthetic Microbiology (SYNMIKRO) at Philipps University Marburg – as well as across the university itself – eLabFTW is offered as a service through the HeFDI (Hessian Research Data Infrastructures) network. Approximately two dozen research groups have already adopted the platform, some using it extensively as a comprehensive electronic lab notebook (ELN), while others use it more selectively for specific tasks, such as booking equipment or managing strain collections. Several additional groups are in the process of transitioning to eLabFTW. Some of these groups previously relied on closed-source ELNs and faced significant challenges with vendor lock-in. The Bioinformatics Core Facility provides support to such users, helping them migrate their data to eLabFTW.

Preventing data loss was a key reason cited by many SYNMIKRO users for adopting an ELN. During a publication revision, they needed to access older experimental data but were initially unable to find the relevant physical lab notebook. When they finally located it, many entries were illegible, forcing them to repeat the experiments to produce reliable data for the reviewers.

Overall, the introduction of eLabFTW has improved the daily work of SYNMIKRO members by making it easier to share data and information. eLabFTW

enables collaborative project work with clear accountability, tracking who performed specific tasks and when.

1.4.4 Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich - Focus: templates and discipline-specific adaptations

Since 2017, Nicolai Siegel's research group in the Department of Physiological Chemistry at LMU Munich's Biomedical Center has been using Benchling to document its collection of macromolecular structures.

Siegel's group was looking for a system that would enable easy creation and sharing of templates and SOPs among lab members, while also facilitating efficient tracking and troubleshooting. Benchling was chosen for its customisation capabilities and functionality. Previously, the group had relied on an old-school folder structure to share common protocols. However, since implementing Benchling, all of their traditional documentation – such as physical lab notebooks, printed gel images, and manual calculations – has been digitised and integrated into the platform. Benchling now allows them to design, store and execute complex experimental protocols that can be easily shared. The platform also offers a clean design and streamlined workflow, as well as the ability to replicate these workflows. As Siegel's group expands, they aim to explore new tools and updates to enhance their workflow and make their use of Benchling more efficient and effective.

Siegel's group also appreciates Benchling's discipline-specific adaptations, such as the bioregistry feature for registering and managing biological entities, the visualisation tools for DNA and protein sequences, and the cloning capabilities.

Some challenges persist, including slow loading times (especially when working with large datasets or at peak times) and potential confusion for new users. Exporting large datasets can also be problematic. The process may take longer than expected due to the size of the data, leading to delays. File size limits or format restrictions might require splitting the data into smaller batches, which can be time-consuming. However, the Benchling support team is always available and responsive, offering guidance and solutions to ensure smooth operations.

Overall, the implementation of Benchling has improved the daily work of Siegel's group members.

2 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank Petra Kneib for her help with the graphic design.

3 FUNDING

This work was supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – project ID 460129525 (NFDI4Microbiota to JV and KUF).

4 CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Chris Allan, Jean-Marie Burel, Josh Moore, Colin Blackburn, Melissa Linkert, Scott Loynton, Donald MacDonald, William J. Moore, Carlos Neves, Andrew Patterson, Michael Porter, Aleksandra Tarkowska, Brian Loranger, Jerome Avondo, Ingvar Lagerstedt, Luca Lianas, Simone Leo, Katherine Hands, Ron T. Hay, Ardan Patwardhan, Christoph Best, Gerard J. Kleywegt, Gianluigi Zanetti, and Jason R. Swedlow. OMERO: flexible, model-driven data management for experimental biology. *Nature Methods*, 9(3):245–253.
- [2] Evgeny Bobrov, Lea-Sophie Adam, Sibylle Söring, Denise Jäckel, Anja Herwig, Birte Lindstädt, and Justine Vandendorpe. Workshop on research data management. Slides, October 2021.
- [3] Steffen Brinckmann, Nicolas CARPi, Manideep Jayavarapu, Florian Rhiem, Stian Soiland-Reyes, and Nico Brandt. The eln file format. <https://github.com/TheELNConsortium/TheELNFileFormat>. Accessed: 2024-07-22.
- [4] Barry Bunin. Going paperless – the move to electronic lab notebooks – Drug Discovery World (DDW) — [ddw-online.com. https://www.ddw-online.com/going-paperless-the-move-to-electronic-lab-notebooks-19943-202210/](https://www.ddw-online.com/going-paperless-the-move-to-electronic-lab-notebooks-19943-202210/), October 2022. [Accessed 24-12-2024].
- [5] Ilaria Ceglia. Electronic lab notebooks: From paper to screen, keeping track of your research. Slides, March 2021.
- [6] Deltablot. eLabFTW — [deltablot.com. https://www.deltablot.com/elabftw/](https://www.deltablot.com/elabftw/), 2024. [Accessed 24-12-2024].
- [7] Getty. 2. what are controlled vocabularies? https://www.getty.edu/research/publications/electronic_publications/intro_controlled_vocab/what.html. Accessed: 2024-09-09.

- [8] Stuart G Higgins, Akemi A Nogiwa-Valdez, and Molly M Stevens. Considerations for implementing electronic laboratory notebooks in an academic research environment. *Nat. Protoc.*, 17(2):179–189, feb 2022.
- [9] Lina-Louise Kaulbach. The Fair Principles: Origin and Meaning - Research Data – Latest News & Worth Knowing — [blog.rwth-aachen.de](https://blog.rwth-aachen.de/forschungsdaten/en/2024/03/14/fair-prinzipien-herkunft-und-bedeutung/#:~:text=In%20March%202016%2C%20the%20FAIR,the%20field%20of%20medical%20genetics.,March%202024.). <https://blog.rwth-aachen.de/forschungsdaten/en/2024/03/14/fair-prinzipien-herkunft-und-bedeutung/#:~:text=In%20March%202016%2C%20the%20FAIR,the%20field%20of%20medical%20genetics.,March%202024.> [Accessed 24-12-2024].
- [10] Jamie Kitman. A brief history of gasoline: Searching for the magic bullet - part 8: People might have put less trust in leaded gasoline if they’d known how much of a shit-show the lab was that invented it. <https://jalopnik.com/a-brief-history-of-gasoline-searching-for-the-magic-bu-1848438134#:~:text=Yet%20none%20of,were%20%E2%80%9Csanitized.%E2%80%9D9,2022.> Accessed: 2024-07-01.
- [11] Evamaria Krause. Elektronische laborbücher im forschungsdatenmanagement – eine neue aufgabe für bibliotheken? *ABI-Tech.*, 36(2):78–87, jul 2016.
- [12] Birte Lindstädt and Justine Vandendorpe. Research data management. Slides, August 2020.
- [13] Brian Nosek. Strategy for culture change. <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change,2019.> Accessed: 2024-07-01.
- [14] University of Pittsburgh Library System. Taxonomies and controlled vocabularies. <https://pitt.libguides.com/metadatadiscovery/controlledvocabularies,September%202023.> Accessed: 2024-09-09.
- [15] openBIS. Jupyter notebooks. [https://openbis.ch/index.php/docs/user-documentation-prior-to-20-10-3/tools-for-analysis-of-data-stored-in-openbis/jupyter-notebooks/.](https://openbis.ch/index.php/docs/user-documentation-prior-to-20-10-3/tools-for-analysis-of-data-stored-in-openbis/jupyter-notebooks/) Accessed: 2024-07-22.
- [16] Torsten Rathmann, Daniela Kastrup, Bastian Weiß, Birte Lindstädt, Aliaksandra Shutsko, and Justine Vandendorpe. Workshop on research data management. Slides, October 2021.
- [17] Longwood Medical Area Research Data Management Working Group (LMA RDMWG). Electronic lab notebooks. <https://datamanagement.hms.harvard.edu/collect-analyze/electronic-lab-notebooks.> Accessed: 2023-11-17.

- [18] Stephanie Rehwald, Sophia Leimer, Birte Lindstädt, Aliaksandra Shutsko, and Justine Vandendorpe. Workshop on research data management in medical and biomedical sciences. Slides, June 2022.
- [19] Olivier Ritme. What is an electronic laboratory notebook? — ritme.com. <https://ritme.com/en/introduction-electronic-laboratory-notebook/>, January 2024. [Accessed 24-12-2024].
- [20] Patrick D. Schloss. Identifying and overcoming threats to reproducibility, replicability, robustness, and generalizability in microbiome research. *mBio*, 9(3), July 2018.
- [21] Gerald Schneikart and Walter Mayrhofer. Revolutionizing solutions of technological assistance for the integration of lab and office activities in biomedical research. *J. Ind. Inf. Integr.*, 26:100333, 2022.
- [22] Max Schröder, Susanne Staehlke, Paul Groth, J. Barbara Nebe, Sascha Spors, and Frank Krüger. Structure-based knowledge acquisition from electronic lab notebooks for research data provenance documentation. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 13(1), January 2022.
- [23] Vega Shah. Electronic Lab Notebook Adoption: Carrot or the Stick? — dotmatics.com. <https://www.dotmatics.com/blog/electronic-lab-notebook-adoption>, August 2022. [Accessed 24-12-2024].
- [24] Stian Soiland-Reyes, Peter Sefton, Mercè Crosas, Leyla Jael Castro, Frederik Coppens, José M. Fernández, Daniel Garijo, Björn Grüning, Marco La Rosa, Simone Leo, Eoghan Ó Carragáin, Marc Portier, Ana Trisovic, RO-Crate Community, Paul Groth, and Carole Goble. Packaging research artefacts with ro-crate. *Data Science*, 5(2):97–138, July 2022.
- [25] NBIS National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden. Controlled vocabularies & ontologies. <https://nbisweden.github.io/module-metadata-dm-practices/02-ontologies/index.html>, 2020 - 2022. Accessed: 2024-09-09.
- [26] Talend. What is Data Mapping? Definition and Examples — talend.com. <https://www.talend.com/resources/data-mapping/>. [Accessed 24-12-2024].
- [27] Justine Vandendorpe, Beatrix Adam, Jeanne Wilbrandt, Birte Lindstädt, and Konrad U. Förstner. Ten simple rules for implementing electronic lab notebooks (elns). *PLOS Computational Biology*, 20(6):1–9, 06 2024.

- [28] Justine Vandendorpe, Jeanne Wilbrandt, Katharina Grünwald, and Maja Magel. Nfdi4microbiota world café on electronic lab notebooks (elns). Slides, February 2023.
- [29] Wiki-authors. Tetraethyllead. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tetraethyllead>. Accessed: 2024-07-01.
- [30] Wiki-authors. Vendor lock-in. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vendor_lock-in. Accessed: 2024-07-01.
- [31] Mark D. Wilkinson, Michel Dumontier, Ijsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, Jan-Willem Boiten, Luiz Bonino da Silva Santos, Philip E. Bourne, Jildau Bouwman, Anthony J. Brookes, Tim Clark, Mercè Crosas, Ingrid Dillo, Olivier Dumon, Scott Edmunds, Chris T. Evelo, Richard Finkers, Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran, Alasdair J.G. Gray, Paul Groth, Carole Goble, Jeffrey S. Grethe, Jaap Heringa, Peter A.C 't Hoen, Rob Hooft, Tobias Kuhn, Ruben Kok, Joost Kok, Scott J. Lusher, Maryann E. Martone, Albert Mons, Abel L. Packer, Bengt Persson, Philippe Rocca-Serra, Marco Roos, Rene van Schaik, Susanna-Assunta Sansone, Erik Schultes, Thierry Sengstag, Ted Slater, George Strawn, Morris A. Swertz, Mark Thompson, Johan van der Lei, Erik van Mulligen, Jan Velterop, Andra Waagmeester, Peter Wittenburg, Katherine Wolstencroft, Jun Zhao, and Barend Mons. The fair guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), March 2016.